

1 Supplementary Information for

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3 **Reply to Weiss et al.:**

4 Tree-ring stable oxygen isotopes suggest an increase in Asian monsoon rainfall at 4.2
5 ka BP

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Table S1. Table S1 Information statistics of speleothem oxygen isotope records used for comparison in this study.

Number of caves	Site name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Temporal resolution (year) ^a	Number of samples ^a	Temporal resolution (year) ^b	Number of samples ^b	Number of dating points	Average dating error (2σ, years)	Series length (cal. yr BP)	References
1	Dongge Cave	25.28	108.08	4.04 ± 0.96	71	4.52 ± 1.52	441	11(2775 ± 59; 3218 ± 66; 3308 ± 48; 3712 ± 84; 3902 ± 50; 4001 ± 46; 4276 ± 73; 4417 ± 38; 4546 ± 72; 4921 ± 63; 5072 ± 51)	59.09	-50~8880	Wang et al., 2005
	Dongge Cave	25.28	108.08	9.93 ± 8.01	32	26.6 ± 24.84	77	8(2627 ± 138; 3218 ± 56; 3625 ± 60; 4034 ± 84; 4152 ± 51; 4260 ± 50; 4629 ± 87; 5167 ± 57)	72.88	-16.5~15810	Dykoski et al., 2005
2	Jiulong Cave	27.8	113.9	21 ± 1.38	13	18.7 ± 5.79	106	6(2589 ± 479; 3317 ± 148;	353.67	101.64~7271.2 3	Zhang et al., 2021

3	Shennong Cave	28.7	117.25	1.88 ±0.56	153	2.73 ±2.45	400	3862 ±87; 4425 ±883; 4936 ±453; 5171 ±72) 12(3707 ±43; 3897 ±47; 4007 ±26; 4117 ±27; 4200 ±30; 4270 ±17; 4452 ±25; 4491 ±46; 4600 ±25; 4814 ±24; 4910 ±17; 5052 ±16) 7(2315 ±50; 3247 ±123; 3601 ±9; 4113 ±136; 4431 ±74; 4664 ±51;5346 ±62) 8(2676 ±17; 4077 ±19; 4202 ±15; 4416 ±23;	28.58	3534.87~4626. 91	Zhang et al., 2021
4	Heifeng Cave	29.02	107.18	37 ±26.25	7	40 ±14.8	49	3601 ±9; 4113 ±136; 4431 ±74; 4664 ±51;5346 ±62) 8(2676 ±17; 4077 ±19; 4202 ±15; 4416 ±23;	83.86	480~11490	Yang et al., 2019
5	Jinfo Cave 13	29.02	107.18	15.56 ±16.43	18	21 ±24.57	91	3601 ±9; 4113 ±136; 4431 ±74; 4664 ±51;5346 ±62) 8(2676 ±17; 4077 ±19; 4202 ±15; 4416 ±23;	19.63	260~10800	Yang et al., 2019

								4397 ±21; 4605 ±16; 4674 ±26; 5388 ±20)				
	Jinfo Cave 12	29.02	107.18	50 ±4.33	5	61.88 ±6	32	2(2348 ±45; 5214 ±23)	34	970~11630	Yang et al., 2019	
6	Shizi Cave	29.68	106.29	29 ±4.33	9	30 ±7.62	66	9(2789 ±469; 3003 ±714; 3552 ±315; 3816 ±211; 4291 ±63; 4329 ±115; 4609 ±95; 4954 ± 143; 5174 ±65)	243.33	20~9270	Yang et al., 2019	
7	Yangzi Cave	29.78	107.78	-	1	173.57 ±0.5	7	2(4695 ±71; 5910 ±32)	51.5	3682~118176	Wu et al., 2020	
8	Heshang Cave	30.45	110.42	13 ±1.02	21	20.64 ±6.9	96	6(2651 ±38; 3211 ±61; 3915 ±63; 4181 ±28; 4181 ±28; 5071 ±95)	52.2	-52~9470	Hu et al., 2008	
9	Sanbao Cave 26	31.67	110.43	17.4 ±0.48	15	18.64 ±0.7	106	4(2660 ±60; 3030 ±40; 3390 ±70; 5320 ±30)	50	403~5229	Dong et al., 2010	

	Sanbao Cave 43	31.67	110.43	22.75 ±5.62	13	21 ±8.1	95	7(2520 ±40; 3050 ±60; 3410 ±60; 3650 ±40; 4020 ±50; 4750 ±50; 5690 ±70) 5(2630 ±60; 3180 ±60;	52.86	70~12863	Dong et al., 2010
	Sanbao Cave 27	31.67	110.43	56	2	29.53 ±28.72	47	3960 ±70; 4640 ±160; 6570 ±90) 9(2998 ±15; 3464 ±15; 3650 ±16; 3998 ±20;	88	2351~8476	Dong et al., 2010
10	Xianglong Cave 26	33	106.33	9.16 ±1.02	31	8.33 ±3.78	237	4479 ±21; 4690 ±17; 4793 ±20; 4835 ±26; 5006 ±23) 8(2893 ±13; 3092 ±13;	19.22	2984~6651	Tan et al., 2018
	Xianglong Cave 16	33	106.33	14.37 ±10.21	19	21.16 ±14.47	90	3197 ±14; 3376 ±12; 3930 ±34;	27	653~4912	Tan et al., 2018

11	Jiuxian Cave C996-1	33.57	109.1	12.4±2.27	23	14.27±7.11	139	4063 ±20; 4163 ±15; 4692 ±65) 5(2920 ±410; 3430 ±100; 3800 ±40; 4000 ± 100; 5040 ±1410) 6(1710 ±110; 3380 ±1150;	412	-48~8614	Cai et al., 2010
	Jiuxian Cave C996-2	33.57	109.1	49.8±0.43	5	39.33±22	49	4310 ±720; 4410 ±400; 4540 ±310; 5280 ±790) 3(2828 ±785;	580	-8~18958	Cai et al., 2010
12	Dongshiya Cave	33.78	110.57	44.61±4.03	6	37.98±19.87	52	4466 ±660; 5542 ±198) 15(2786 ±103; 3018 ±49; 3194 ±28; 3459 ±34;	547.7	-58~8672	Zhang et al., 2018
13	Wuya Cave Composite	33.82	105.43	2.91±1.73	99	3.3±1.7	556	3628 ±39; 3654 ±31; 3774 ±35; 3890 ± 51; 3996 ±37; 4082 ±48; 4227 ±42; 4315 ±	55.3	2687~6063	Tan et al., 2020

								75; 4491±41; 4668±101; 5068±116) 3(4448±55;				
	Wuya Cave 14	33.82	105.43	-	-	3.56±0.49	194	4836±77; 5086±53) 15(2786±103; 3018±493; 194±28; 3459±34; 3628±39; 3654±31; 3774±35;	61.67	4308~6183	Tan et al., 2020	
	Wuya Cave 12	33.82	105.43	2.91±1.73	99	4.53±16.67	441	3890±51; 3996±37; 4082±48; 4227±42; 4315±75; 4491±41; 4668±101) 4(4863±201;	55.33	2687~6063	Tan et al., 2020	
14	Baeg-nyong Cave	37.27	128.58	14.74±3.27	19	19.11±8.22	104	4084±294; 3419±343; 2954±91)	232.3	0~5437	Jo et al., 2017	
15	Lianhua Cave 9	38.17	113.72	23.5±0.29	12	25.36±27.47	58	2(3048±249; 4176±104)	176.5	1289~4484	Dong et al., 2015	
16	Zhenzhu Cave	38.26	113.72	62.33±0.5	3	75±21	26	3(2326±295;	5199	1264~-130363	Li et al., 2020	

								4566 ±6278; 5310 ±9024 5(2307 ±97; 3213 ±317;				
17	Liu-li Cave	41.02	125.82	17.58 ±6.53	15	20.3 ±36.14	98	3930 ±214; 4773 ±129; 5505 ±83)	168	-54~6682	Zhao et al., 2021	
18	Water Cave	41.28	124.07	22.27 ±16.04	11	30.14 ±11.68	64	-		388~4914	Tan et al., 2005	
19	Nuanhuo Cave	41.33	124.92	36.72	6	42.93	39	3(1803 ±91; 3363 ±171; 4729 ±130)	130.7	897~5376	Wu et al., 2011	
20	Kesang Cave (KS06-A-H)	42.86	81.75	2.5 ±4.517	8	36.67 ±4.25	39	2(3800 ±60; 5490 ±30) 5(2523 ±1079; 3772 ±3580;	45	3570~9440	Cheng et al., 2016	
21	Kesang Cave (CNKS-7)	42.86	81.75	32 ±7.13	8	31.16 ±19.45	62	4603 ±91; 4700 ±487; 5371 ±129) 4(3250 ±608;	5366	1495~10220	Cai et al., 2017	
22	Kesang Cave (CNKS-9)	42.86	81.75	12.21 ±0.16	22	13.79 ±3.16	144	3937 ±757; 3757 ±583;5205 ± 2737) 18(3776 ±14;	1171.2	-157.57~3522.1 7	Cai et al., 2017	
23	Gol-e-Zard Cave (GZ14-1)	35.84	81.75	11.16 ±5.22	25	4.45 ±4.18	259	3855 ±13; 3861 ±12; 3876 ±14;	12.56	3766~4920	Carolin et al., 2019	

									3886 ±11; 3902 ±11; 3906 ±14; 3916 ±13; 3927 ±15; 3969 ±12; 4007 ±13; 4076 ±12; 4178 ±11; 4274 ±11; 4324 ±13; 4389 ±14; 4394 ±11; 4437 ±12)			
24	Mawmluh Cave (KM-A)	25.26	81.75	5.87	49	6.05 ±1.21	222	27.33	3(5048 ±32, 4112 ±30, 3654 ±20) 18(3779 ±14; 3855 ±13; 3861 ±12; 3876 ±14; 3886 ±11; 3902 ±11; 3906 ±14; 3916 ±13; 3927 ±15; 3969 ±12; 4007 ±13; 4076 ±12; 4178 ±11; 4274 ±11; 4324 ±13;	3653~12395	Berkelhammer et al., 2012	
25	Mawmluh Cave (ML.1)	25.26	81.75	0.99 ±0.55	292	0.68 ±0.61	970	12.6	3778~4440	Kathayat et al., 2018		

26	Mawmluh Cave (ML.2)	25.26	81.75	2.74±1.97	105	4.93±4.91	237	4389 ±14; 4394 ±11; 4437 ±12) 5(3479 ±16; 3829 ±13; 4214 ±13; 4438 ±21; 4541 ±17) 17(2811 ±143; 3018 ±80; 3068 ±42; 3258 ±39; 3485 ±57; 3529 ±44; 3957 ±72; 4033 ±87; 4162 ±155; 4254 ±96; 4489 ±114; 4500 ±147; 4502 ±137; 4634 ±50; 4685 ±84; 4979 ±124; 5318 ±141)	16	3366~4534	Kathayat et al., 2018
27	Sahiya Cave (SAH2)	30.6	81.75	9.35±3.23	30	2.35±2.48	851	4033 ±87; 4162 ±155; 4254 ±96; 4489 ±114; 4500 ±147; 4502 ±137; 4634 ±50; 4685 ±84; 4979 ±124; 5318 ±141)	94.8	2650~5706	Kathayat et al., 2017

^a indicates the periods of 3.97-4.26 ka BP; ^b indicates the periods of 3-5 ka BP.

4.26-3.97 (cal. kaBP)

No. of cave	Site name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Temporal resolution(Year)	Sample numbers	Temporal resolution (year)
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1	Dongge Cave	25.2833	108.0833	4.04±0.96	71	4.52±1.52
	Dongge Cave	25.2833	108.0833	9.93±8.01	32	26.6±24.84
2	Jiulong Cave	27.8	113.9	21±1.38	13	18.7±5.79
3	Shennong Cave	28.7	117.25	1.88±0.56	153	2.73±2.45
4	Heifeng Cave	29.0167	107.1792	37±26.25	7	40±14.8
5	Jinfo Cave 13	29.0167	107.1792	15.56±16.43	18	21±24.57
	Jinfo Cave 12	29.0167	107.1792	50±4.33	5	61.88±6
6	Shizi Cave	29.6822	106.2881	29±4.33	9	30±7.62
7	Yangzi Cave	29.7833	107.7833		1	173.57±0.5

8	Heshang Cave	30.45	110.4167	13±1.02	21	20.64±6.9
9	Sanbao Cave 26	31.6667	110.4333	17.4±0.48	15	18.64±0.7
	Sanbao Cave 43	31.6667	110.4333	22.75±5.62	13	21±8.1
	Sanbao Cave 27	31.6667	110.4333	56	2	29.53±28.72
10	Xianglong Cave 26	33	106.3333	9.16±1.02	31	8.33±3.78
	Xianglong Cave 16	33	106.3333	14.37±10.21	19	21.16±14.47
11	Jiuxian Cave C996-1	33.5667	109.1	12.4±2.27	23	14.27±7.11
	Jiuxian Cave C996-2	33.5667	109.1	49.8±0.43	5	39.33±22
12	Dongshiya Cave	33.7833	110.5667	44.61±4.03	6	37.98±19.87

13	Wuya Cave Composite	33.8176	105.4333	2.91±1.73	99	3.3±1.7
	Wuya Cave 14	33.8176	105.4333	无	无	3.56±0.49
	Wuya Cave 12	33.8176	105.4333	2.91±1.73	99	4.53±16.67
14	Baeg-nyong Cave	37.272	128.579	14.74±3.27	19	19.11±8.22

15	Lianhua Cave 9	38.1667	113.7167	23.5±0.29	12	25.36±27.47
16	Zhenzhu Cave	38.26	113.72	62.33±0.5	3	75±21
17	Liu-li Cave	41.0167	125.8167	17.58±6.53	15	20.3±36.14
18	Water Cave	41.2833	124.0667	22.27±16.04	11	30.14±11.68
19	Nuanhuo Cave	41.333	124.9167	36.72	6	42.93
20	Kesang Cave (KS06-A-H)	42.86	81.75	2.5±4.517	8	36.67±4.25
21	Kesang Cave (CNKS-7)	42.86	81.75	32±7.13	8	31.16±19.45
22	Kesang Cave(CNKS-9)	42.86	81.75	12.21±0.16	22	13.79±3.16

25	Gol-e-Zard Cave (GZ14-1)	35.84	81.75	11.16±5.22	25	4.45±4.18
26	Mawmluh Cave	25.2622	81.75	5.87	49	6.05±1.21
27	Mawmluh Cave (ML.1)	25.2622	81.75	0.99±0.55	292	0.68±0.61
28	Mawmluh Cave (ML.2)	25.2622	81.75	2.74±1.97	105	4.93±4.91
29	Sahiya Cave (SAH2)	30.6	81.75	9.35±3.23	30	2.35±2.48

Fig. S1. Comparison of normalized speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records (thin line) from different parts of central Asia spanning 5–3 ka (for detailed information of each record, see *SI Appendix, Table S1*). Each record is interpolated annually, and then their linear trends are removed before normalization. A composite of all the normalized series and 95% CIs (yellow shading) for central Asia is shown. A 100-point low-pass filter (heavy line) is applied in each normalized series to highlight centennial variability. The grey bar covers the period 3.97–4.26 ka.

Fig. S2. Comparison of normalized speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records (thin line) from different parts of northern China and northeast Asia spanning 5–3 ka (for detailed information of each record, see *SI Appendix, Table S1*). Each record is interpolated annually, and then their linear trends are removed before normalization. A composite of all the normalized series and 95% CIs (yellow shading) is shown. A 100-point low-pass filter (heavy line) is applied in each normalized series to highlight centennial variability. The grey bar covers the period 3.97–4.26 ka.

Fig. S3. Comparison of normalized speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records (thin line) from different parts of southern China spanning 5–3 ka (for detailed information of each record, see *SI Appendix, Table S1*). Each record is interpolated annually, and then their linear trends are removed before normalization. A 100-yr low-pass filter is applied to each series to highlight centennial fluctuations. The grey bar covers the

period 3.97–4.26 ka. A regional composite and 95% CIs (yellow shading) for southern China is shown, which is derived by averaging the six higher-resolution normalized speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ series from Dongge Cave, Xianglong Cave, Wuya Cave, Sanbao Cave 43, Heshang Cave and Shennong Cave using Z-score method. Each of the six speleothem records has a temporal resolution better than 20 years, at least 5 U-Th ages and dating precision higher than 60-yr average age error (2σ) in the 5–3 ka interval. A 100-point low-pass filter (heavy line) is applied in each normalized series to highlight low-frequency variability.

Fig. S4. Comparison of speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records (thin line) from different parts of the Indian subcontinent spanning 5–3 ka (for detailed information of each record, see *SI Appendix, Table S1*). Each record is interpolated annually, and then their linear trends are removed before normalization. A composite of all the normalized series and 95% CIs (yellow shading) is shown. A 100-yr low-pass filter is applied to each series to highlight centennial fluctuations. The grey bar covers the period 3.97–4.26 ka.

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